
SKILLS REQUIRED OF OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT LECTURERS FOR INSTRUCTIONAL DELIVERY IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN NORTH CENTRAL STATES OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The advent of the 21st century has brought about significant transformations in the educational landscape particularly in the realm of instructional delivery. The rapid evolution of technology and the increasing demand for digital literacy have necessitated the acquisition of specialized skills by educators. The integration of entrepreneurship and word processing skills is crucial for effective instructional delivery in institutions of learning. The main purpose of this study is to determine the difference in the entrepreneurship and word processing skills required by lecturers of State and Federal Colleges of Education for instructional delivery. The population consists of lecturers from these higher educational institutions of learning. A sample of 108, lecturers was selected using. A structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference in entrepreneurship skills and word processing skills needed by lecturers from both State and Federal Colleges of Education for instructional delivery. This suggests that lecturers from both State and Federal Colleges of Education require similar levels of entrepreneurship and word processing skills to effectively deliver instructions. The findings of this study have implications for teachers training and development programmes, emphasizing the need for uniform standards in entrepreneurship and word processing skills training for lecturers across State and Federal Colleges of Education. The limitations of the study include its reliance on self-reported data and its exploration of the impact of entrepreneurship skills on instructional delivery a previously under-researched area in business education.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship skills, word processing, Instruction delivery, office technology management lecturers, colleges of education.

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly changing technological environment, office technology management (OTM) lecturers play an important role in equipping students with necessary skills to succeed in the modern workforce. To effectively deliver instruction in colleges of education, OTM lecturers must possess a unique blend of entrepreneurship skills and word processing skills. This introduction highlights the importance of these skills and provides an overview of the key competencies required for effective instructional delivery.

Instructional delivery is a critical component of the educational sector as it determines the effectiveness of teaching and learning processes (Edeh & Olupayimo, 2023). It encompasses the methods, techniques and tools employed by educators to transfer knowledge and skills to students (Gonzalez- Perez, & Montoyo, 2021). In the context of colleges of education subsector, instructional delivery plays an important role on preparing future educators and professionals who can contribute to national development. Colleges of Education, particularly in Nigeria are responsible for training teachers and professionals in various disciplines including office technology management (OTM)

Office technology and management education (OTME) is formally known as secretariat studies; the curriculum was reviewed and renamed office technology management (OTM) by National Board for Technical Education (NBTE, 2004). Since then Polytechnics, Colleges of Education and University have adopted the name OTM. Nwosu (2022) asserted that office education has been structured to equip its recipients with necessary knowledge, attitude and practical skills towards achieving economic development and ensuring self reliance among its graduates. Hence, office education is the key business education programme that enables students to learn variety of computer applications and office skills required to work as secretary, teaching of business subjects, entrepreneurial and administrative support positions (Okoli & Okolo, 2024). Ojowoh (2014) defined office education as an effective, efficient, productive and functional educational programme which prepares graduates for self employment, paid employment and self realization. The objective of office as imbedded on business education programme includes to produce competent NCE graduates who will teach business subjects in secondary schools, and other related educational institutions to produce and commence the development of much desired revolution in vocational and entrepreneurial skills, from the primary through secondary schools, to equip graduates with the right business competencies for a life of work in the office as well as for self employment among others (NCCE, 2020). It could be deduced from the aforementioned that the objectives of the programme was packaged to equip students with knowledge, competencies, and specific skills to enable them function as business studies teachers in public and private sectors of the economy and successfully hold positions as office managers, administrative assistant, entrepreneurs as well as being self reliant on graduation.

Business education is a comprehensive field of study that imparts knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values essential for effective participation in the business world (Ezeani, 2012). It encompasses various disciplines, including accounting, marketing, management, entrepreneurship, office technology, aiming to prepare individuals for diverse roles within the business sector. Business education programme has no single acceptable definition this is because new technologies have emerged which is making some definitions made decades ago obsolete. But the definitions provided by experts in the field revolve round knowledge, skills and competencies that will make individual succeed in business.

Akeke et al., (2022) describe business education as the combination of different courses designed to provide learners with several number of skills required for success in business,

particularly those linked to launching and running new business ventures. Obidile and Onyeagba, (2019) defined business education as a specific curriculum of training planned to offer individual with knowledge, abilities and attitude for professional work and progression. It is also a course of study which prepares its beneficiary with pertinent skills required by students to be fruitful in the society. This field of business education happens at many levels, including post primary and tertiary education institution. It is a programme who intends to attain these objectives by preparing their students for the world of work either as employees or employers of labour (Gontur & Tuamyil, 2023). Business education educators introduce students to the basics of personal finance, the decision-making techniques needed to be wise consumers, the economic principles of an increasingly international marketplace, and the processes by which businesses operate (Gontur et al., 2023).

Business educators play a prominent role in preparing students to become responsible citizens, capable of making the astute economic decisions that will benefit their personal and professional lives. It provides training, skills; knowledge and abilities which could enable their students achieve self-reliance after graduation. It is therefore expected that business education students upon graduation should be able to venture into entrepreneurial activities and thrive successfully, instead of being unemployed or waiting for white collar jobs that are not readily available. In spite of these aims and expectations, lack of job competencies by universities graduates and high rate of graduate unemployment in the society as ascertained by some scholars like Okolie et al., (2021); Obidile, Amobi and Uzoekwe (2017) create doubts as to the adequacy of the tertiary education programmes to impart the relevant competencies necessary to meet the demands of the entrepreneurial development. Entrepreneurship skills are critical competencies that enable individuals to identify opportunities to bring out solutions, and effectively manage resources for business success. These skills are particularly significant in office technology management (OTM), where they prepare individuals to handle technological advancements and dynamic business environment. Osuala (2004) defined entrepreneurship skills are essential competencies that enable individuals to pursue self reliant career or manage organizations innovatively. In addition, Musa, (2023) highlight entrepreneurial skills as a combination of technical, managerial and problem solving abilities aimed at improving efficiency and productivity. Entrepreneurship skills (ES) empowers students to develop innovative, and self creative skills for sustaining career paths, enabling them identify business opportunities, manage resources and developing successful business enterprises (Gontur, 2016; Gontur & Tuamyil, 2023). Given the rising unemployment rate in Nigeria incorporating entrepreneurship into instructional delivery is a strategic approach to equip students with the mindset and capabilities to create their own employment opportunities (Onuma, 2016).

Word processing skill is important in the application of e-learning for improve instructional delivery of office education programme especially in colleges of education. It is an important tool that enhances the information management functions of office education graduate. Ezenwafor & Okolo (2020) posited that word processing is the application of computer technology to the inputting, editing, merging, storing, formatting and printing of text. Nwosu (2023) explained that word processing is the use of automated equipment to produce such document as letters, reports and other text materials. In the words of Haigh (2006), word processing is the use of computer to handle text and produce typed and/or printed document. Onyewuenyi (2024) stipulated that word processing is the writing, editing and production of documents such as letters, reports and books through the use of a computer programmed or a complete computer system designed to facilitate rapid and efficient manipulation of text. Ikpah and Azih (2024) also stated that the application of word processing in e-learning can

improved instructional delivery of office education programme especially in colleges of education.

Similarly, word processing skills are foundation in OTM education as they enable students to perform essential office tasks such as document creation, editing and formatting (Ezenwafor, & Okolo, 2020). These skills are integral to preparing students for modern office environment where skills in micro soft word, Google docs, and other office software is a minimum requirement OTM lecturers most possess advanced word processing skills must possess advanced word processing skills to provide first hand training and preparing students to meet industry standard (Uduafemhe, Ewim, & Karfe, 2023).

Both entrepreneurship and word technical skill (word processing) contribute to the employability and productivity of graduates making them indispensable components of instructional delivery in business education (Gontur & Tuamyil, 2023). The relationship between entrepreneurship skills (ES) and word processing (WPS) in OTM have a mutual association. Entrepreneurship skills equip students with the ability to conceptualize and manage business ideas (Sousa, 2018), Word processing skills provides the technical proficiency needed to execute administrative and managerial tasks effectively, for instance, effective entrepreneurship requires the ability to create business proposal, financial reports and marketing management all of which depend on advanced word process skills (Ikpah & Azih, 2024). Thus, the integration of these competencies into the instructional delivery ensures that students are futuristically prepared to the demands of modern workplace.

Existing studies such as Ogunode and Musa (2020), Ogunyinka et al., (2015) and Shaibu et al, (2019) have explored the challenges of instructional delivery in Nigerian Colleges of Education, but to have often overlooked the specific skills set required for effective OTM education, while some research has emphasized entrepreneurship education (Nwalwu, 2023). There is limited focus on its integration with technical skills like word processing in the OTM context. In addition, most studies do not address the unique challenges faced by lecturers in North Central Nigeria; this region is characterized by farmers and headers clashes and terrorism that has affected academic activities especially in Niger, Benue and Plateau State (Ajodo- Adebajoko & Nwakor, 2024). This gap necessitated a comprehensive investigation into the nexus of entrepreneurship and word processing skills in instructional delivery and the barriers to their effective implementation

The motivation for this study arises from the pressing need to improve the quality of OTM education in North Central Nigeria. By addressing the gaps in lecturers' competencies, the study aims to enhance instructional delivery and prepared for the demands of the workforce. The study also seeks to align OTM education with national development goals, particularly in promoting entrepreneurship and technical skills (Musa, 2023). Furthermore, this study aims to provide evidence based recommendations for policy and practice contributing to the broader objectives of revitalizing the education sector in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The efficacy of pedagogical delivery within institutions of higher education is profoundly shaped by the expertise of educators, particularly within office technology and management (OTM) curricula. Instructors are anticipated to demonstrate proficient entrepreneurial and word processing capabilities to effectively prepare students for the contemporary labor market. However, empirical evidence suggests that OTM educators in North-Central Nigeria may exhibit deficiencies in these critical skill sets. Investigative work conducted by Ezech (2018) and Edeh et al. (2023) has illuminated inadequacies in computer proficiency, a lack of

skills in office practices, shorthand, typewriting/keyboarding, word processing, computer literacy, office management, business communication, and entrepreneurial skills prevalent among OTM educators in Nigeria. Correspondingly, this underscores the imperative for augmented training in word processing software applications to enhance pedagogical delivery. Furthermore, research conducted by Okorojiofor and Areji (2023) has determined that OTM students necessitate robust word processing abilities for proficient performance in contemporary office environments, indicating that the competencies of educators have a direct bearing on the preparedness of students. Additionally, the incorporation of entrepreneurial skills into the curriculum is vital for promoting self-sufficiency and innovation among learners. A study by Ezeani and Urama (2014) underscores the significance of entrepreneurial skill development in business education, asserting that educators must be adequately equipped to effectively transmit these competencies. The discernible deficiencies in entrepreneurial and word processing skills among OTM educators may result in substandard pedagogical delivery, thereby negatively impacting the educational quality and students' readiness for the professional sphere. This study intends to examine the specific entrepreneurial and word processing skills requisite for OTM educators within Colleges of Education in North Central Nigeria, identify prevailing deficiencies, and propose methodologies for enhancing instructional efficacy.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to identify the skill improvement needs of Business Education Lecturers of OTM courses in Colleges of Education in North Central States of Nigeria. Specifically the study determined the:

- i. Entrepreneurship skills required of OTM Lecturers for instructional delivery in Colleges of Education in North- Central States of Nigeria.
- ii. Word processing skills required of OTM Lecturers for instructional delivery in Colleges of Education in North- Central States of Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the entrepreneurship education skills required of OTM Lecturers for instructional delivery in Colleges of Education in North- Central States of Nigeria?
- ii. What is the word processing skills required of OTM Lecturers for instructional delivery in Colleges of Education in North- Central States of Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant difference between the mean response of OTM lecturers from Federal and State Colleges of Education on entrepreneurship education skills required for instructional delivery in North- central states of Nigeria.
- ii. There is no significant difference between the mean response of OTM lecturers from Federal and State Colleges of Education on word processing skills required for instructional delivery in North- central states of Nigeria.

METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive survey design, in the views of Olaitan, Ali, Eyoh, and Sowande (2000), the survey research design is the plan structure and strategy the investigator wants to adopt to obtain solutions to research problems and test hypotheses formulated for the study. They further stated that it guides the investigator in collecting analysis and interpreting

observations. The design was therefore appropriate for this study since it obtained data from lecturers of state and federal colleges of education through a structured questionnaire on the application of these skills by the lecturers'. The study was carried out in the North Central Zone of Nigeria; the zone comprises Benue, Plateau, Nasarawa, Kogi, Kwara, Niger State, and the Federal Capital Territory. The study area was chosen because the demographic characteristics of the lecturers are a reflection of the entire country; this zone has almost all the tribes you think are in Nigeria, and the administrative seat of government in Abuja attracts employees from all the states in Nigeria. Secondly, with the high level of graduates migrating from other zones to the FCT for green pastures, it is relevant for business educators to emphasize the teaching of entrepreneurial skills that would help learners to become self-employed after graduation. The population for the study was 108 lecturers, which comprised 31 lecturers from four Federal Colleges of Education and 77 lecturers of OTM specialization from ten State Colleges of Education in the 2022/2023 academic session in the North-Central geopolitical zone in Nigeria. The sample size was drawn from across fourteen Colleges of Education in North Central Nigeria. The Total Population Sample (TPS) of OTM lecturers was used for the study. TPS, according to Crossman (2018), is the sampling technique that a researcher chooses to examine the entire population that has one or more shared characteristics. Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim (2016) described TPS as a technique where the entire population that meets the criteria (e.g., specific skill set, experience, etc.) is included in the research being conducted. Based on the foregoing, the entire 108 lecturers were used for the study.

The data collected were organized and analyzed using statistical tools such as mean and standard deviation (SD). Mean ratings of 2.50 and above were considered accepted (A), while means below 2.50 were not accepted (NA) to test the research questions, and t-test was used to test the hypotheses of the study at a 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Table1: Entrepreneurship Education Skills Required of OTM Lecturers for Instructional Delivery in Colleges of Education in North Central Nigeria

S/N	Statement	Federal		State		g \bar{X}	Remark
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
		NF=31		NS=77			
1.	Constantly see business opportunities or ideas that have commercial values	2.87	1.02	2.56	1.09	2.72	A
2.	Grow or build businesses	3.13	1.12	3.21	1.11	3.17	A
3.	I am creative and i regularly come up with new ideas	3.09	1.09	3.06	1.06	3.08	A
4.	I proffer solutions to business problems	2.78	1.11	2.94	1.09	2.41	NA
5.	I stand my ground even in difficult decision	2.76	1.09	3.17	1.01	2.97	A
6.	I come up with more than one way to solve problem	2.97	1.12	2.56	1.09	2.77	A
7.	I am decisive when making important decisions in business	3.10	1.09	3.21	1.11	3.16	A
8.	Look at business problems from all angles to find the best solution	3.16	1.11	3.10	1.10	3.13	A
9.	I am active, have functional skills	3.02	1.07	3.26	1.09	3.14	A

and ideas to create jobs							
10. I explore government programmes for entrepreneurship	2.85	1.14	2.99	1.03	2.92	A	
Cluster Mean	2.97	1.10	2.92	1.08	2.94	A	

The data in table 1 indicates that federal and state lecturers accepted to have possessed nine entrepreneurship education skills required of OTM lecturers for instructional delivery in colleges of education. The mean responses for these items 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, and 10 were 2.50 and above. Item 4, was less than 2.50, federal and state lecturers did not accept to possess entrepreneurship skills. The aggregate cluster mean and standard deviation response for federal colleges of education 2.97 and standard deviation of 1.10 while lecturers from the State Colleges of Education have cluster mean of 2.92 and a standard deviation of 1.08. From the results above, the study conclude that there is no difference in the mean response between state and federal colleges of education on entrepreneurship skills required by OTM lecturers for effective instructional delivery.

Table 2: Word Processing Skills Required of OTM Lecturers For Instructional Delivery in Colleges of Education.

S/N	Statement	Federal NF=31 NS=77		State		g \bar{X}	Remark
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
1.	Typing using appropriate finger skills	2.87	1.00	2.56	1.09	2.72	A
2.	Search for words/characters as appropriate	2.86	1.05	3.21	1.11	3.04	A
3.	Replace words/characters as appropriate	2.09	1.09	2.06	1.06	2.08	NA
4.	Spell check for errors	3.78	1.11	2.04	1.09	2.91	A
5.	Correct the errors	2.76	1.09	2.17	1.01	2.47	NA
6.	Recall/retrieve documents	2.97	1.12	2.56	1.09	2.77	A
7.	Store documents	3.23	1.09	3.21	1.11	3.22	A
8.	Erase documents	2.66	1.11	3.01	1.01	2.88	A
9.	Use different word processing packages like MS word, WordPerfect, WordStar	3.02	1.07	2.61	1.09	2.82	A
10.	Use communication packages like e-mail	2.85	1.14	2.99	1.03	2.92	A
	Cluster Mean	2.91	1.09	2.65	1.08	2.78	A

The data in table 2 indicates that federal and state lecturers accepted to have possessed eight word processing skills required of OTM lecturers for instructional delivery in colleges of education. The mean responses for these items 1, 2, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 were 2.50 and above. Items 3 and 5 were less than 2.50, federal and state lecturers did not accept to possess entrepreneurship skills. The aggregate cluster mean and standard deviation response for federal colleges of education 2.91 and standard deviation of 1.09 while lecturers from the State Colleges of Education have cluster mean of 2.65 and a standard deviation of 1.08. From the results above, the study conclude that there is no difference in the mean response between

state and federal colleges of education on word processing skills required by OTM lecturers for effective instructional delivery.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of lecturers in Federal College of Education and State Colleges of Education on entrepreneurship skills required by them for effective instructional delivery in North Central

Table 3: T test results on entrepreneurship skills required by OTM Lecturers for instructional delivery

Lecturers	N	Mean	SD	Df	t- cal	t- crit	Decision
Federal Colleges of Education	31	2.97	1.12	106	.789	1.96	NS
State Colleges of Education	77	3.23	1.09				

Note N= Number, SD= Standard Deviation, Df= Degree of Freedom t- cal = t calculated, t crit = t critical from the table.

From the table 3, the calculated t-value of .789 is less than the t-tabulated value of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance for the two-tailed test and 106 degrees of freedom. Since t cal is less than t critical value, the test is not statistically significant. This means the null hypothesis is retained; this means that there is no significant difference on entrepreneurship skills required by both lecturers in Federal and State colleges of education for delivery of instructions. The study finding holds an important implication for policy and practice in the education sector. The lack of a significant difference suggests that lecturers in both levels of competence, access to resources, ad adherence to standard curricula for teaching entrepreneurship skills and delivery instruction. This uniformity may be attributed to the centralized accreditation and regulatory mechanisms overseen by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) in Nigeria, which ensures standardization in the training and performance expectations of lecturers across institutions. Furthermore, the findings may indicate that OTM lecturers, regardless of the type of institution face common challenges might include those OTM lecturers, regardless of the type of institution face common challenges might include limited access to modern teaching technologies, insufficient professional development opportunities.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of lecturers in Federal College of Education and State Colleges of Education on word processing skills required by them for effective instructional delivery in North Central

Table 4: T test results on word processing skills required by OTM Lecturers for instructional delivery

Lecturers	N	Mean	SD	Df	t- cal	t- crit	Decision
Federal Colleges of Education	31	3.10	1.09	106	.611	1.96	NS
State Colleges of Education	77	3.06	1.06				

Note N= Number, SD= Standard Deviation, Df= Degree of Freedom t- cal = t calculated, t crit = t critical from the table.

From the table 4, the calculated t-value of .611 is less than the t-tabulated value of 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance for the two-tailed test and 106 degrees of freedom. Since t cal is less than t critical value, the test is not statistically significant. This means the null hypothesis is retained; this means that there is no significant difference in the word processing skills required by both lecturers in Federal and State Colleges of Education in delivery of instructions.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study findings revealed no significant difference in the entrepreneurship skills required for instructional delivery between lecturers from state and federal colleges of education in North Central Nigeria. This suggests that lecturers from both types of institutions possess similar levels of entrepreneurship skills, which are essential for effective instructional delivery. The result of the findings could be due to homogeneity in lecturer training, equal emphasis on entrepreneurship education, access to resources and adherence to curricula for teaching entrepreneurship skills and delivery of instruction. For example Tarhan (2021) investigated the entrepreneurship skills of educational institutions in Poland found that training opportunities in entrepreneurship skills ensure that lecturers in tertiary institutions whether public and private are the same for effective delivery of instructions. Furthermore, Yussof and Lame (2017) highlighted that entrepreneurial competencies are relevant and critical for lecturers teaching entrepreneurship courses in higher educational institutions. It was also discovered that instructors must possess some basic entrepreneurship skills for effective teaching to their students as well as to develop students' entrepreneurial skills and knowledge which are considered necessary for new venture management and new venture creation. Also the finding is in diadem of Gidado and Akaeze (2014) who asserted that acquisition and utilisation of the right entrepreneurship skills promote entrepreneurship in lecturers and students. The result of hypothesis two indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean rating between word processing skills required by lecturers in state and federal colleges of education in North Central Nigeria for effective instructional delivery to OTM students. This implies that word processing skills required for instruction delivery are consistent across both state and federal institutions. The uniformity suggests that OTM lecturers in both types of institutions are expected to meet similar standards in their ability to use word processing tools for tasks such as preparing lecture notes, designing instructional materials, creating assessments and maintaining administrative records. The lack of significant difference may also indicate that training, professional development programmes and curriculum requirement for OTM lecturers are standardized, ensuring parity in the skills required for effective instructional delivery. The finding is in agreement with the work of Ikpah & Azih (2024) who indicate that word processing skills and micro soft excel skills are e learning tools use to improve instructional delivering of office skills in Colleges of Education in Cross River State. Furthermore, this result supported by the findings of Break and Tondeur (2014) who noted that most teachers use technology tools such as e mail, the internet and other software applications daily to help create, obtain and communicate information effectively from one person to another. They use many educators as it improves the students' quality of learning and enhance employability. The result also collaborates the view of MTLSS (2017) who indicated that the influence of e- learning is teaching and learning of Microsoft, word skills is that it helps select text and make change to font including changing the font size type, style and effects (bold, underline, italics, and colour), cut, copy, and paste text, use undo and redo, icons, select and resize, graphics, pictures, and select multimedia chips, create a new file using, save as, use page set up etc.

IMPLICATIONS

The absence of significant difference in entrepreneurship skills and word processing skills required by lecturers of federal and state colleges of education, it implies that uniform training programmes can focus on enhancing entrepreneurship and word processing skills, benefiting lecturers from both federal and state colleges. This uniformity can also facilitate the sharing of resources expertise and best practices in entrepreneurship and word processing education instituted collaboration is another implication, as lecturers can engage in collaborative can lead to improved instructional delivery and better student outcomes.

Furthermore, a standard and evaluation framework can be used to assess lecturers' entrepreneurship skills and word processing skills ensuring consistency and fairness. The practical implication also suggest that federal and state colleges of education can work together to develop and implement entrepreneurship skills and word processing programmes. This collaboration can lead to more efficient use of resources, improved programme quality and better student outcomes.

Under the theoretical implication, it suggests that entrepreneurship theories and models can be applied universally across Federal and State Colleges of Education. This generalisability implies that researchers can develop a unified understanding of entrepreneurship and word processing skills required for instructional delivery. The findings also imply that entrepreneurial education can be designed and delivered in a context that is independent; this means that the same entrepreneurship programmes can be effective in both federal and state colleges of education in Nigeria regardless of the specific contexts. Furthermore, existing entrepreneurship theories and models can be validated and applied across both institutions. It also suggest that researchers can develop a more comprehensive understanding of entrepreneurship and word processing skills required for instructional delivery by OTM lecturers. This understanding can inform the development of more effective entrepreneurship education programmes leading to better students outcomes.

The absence of significant differences in entrepreneurship skills and computer skills required by lecturers has several implications; it suggests that a uniform policy framework can be developed to guide lecturers in the implementation of curriculum designed by National Commission for Colleges of Education in Nigeria. This framework can help tutors to develop and implement of the curriculum on entrepreneurship and office technology management programmes in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the entrepreneurship and word processing skills needed by lecturers of several federal and state colleges of education in instructional delivery. The findings revealed that no significant difference in entrepreneurship skills and word processing skills required by lecturers of federal and state colleges of education. The findings of this study have significant implication for practice, theory and policy. Uniform training programmes, collaborative professional development opportunities, and standardized evaluation frameworks can be developed to enhance lecturers' entrepreneurship and word processing skills. The study's results also support the generalisability of entrepreneurship theories and models across federal and state colleges of education. This study contributes to the existing literature on entrepreneurship education by highlighting the similarities' in entrepreneurship skills and word processing skills required by lecturers of Federal and State Colleges of Education. The study's findings have significant implications on enhancing the quality of entrepreneurship and instructional delivery in colleges of education.

The study's limitations include its reliance on self-reported data, which may be subject to bias, and its focus on specific geographic region, North Central Nigeria, potentially limiting the generalisability of the findings to other zones in Nigeria. Additionally, this study did not account for other important skills such as power point skills, and other analytical tools that are needed by OTM lecturers for instructional delivery of business education content with emphasises on courses such as information and communication and computer related courses. Future study should consider incorporating a wider range of data resources and expanding to other zones to enhance generalisability of the results. Expanding the sample size, carrying out

longitudinal studies to evaluate the long-term effects of entrepreneurship skills, word processing skills and the instructional materials by tutors for effective delivery of educational outcomes should be the main goals of future studies. This will provide an expanded view of how teaching training in vocational skills can influenced instructional delivery.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study

1. It is recommended that state and federal colleges of education should develop uniform entrepreneurship training programmes for lecturers as no significant difference in entrepreneurship skills required for instructional delivery was found between the two types of institutions.
2. It is recommended that state and federal colleges of education should provide standardized training programmes to enhance lecturers' word processing skills as these skills are essential for effective infrastructural delivery regardless of institution types.

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